

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTANCES RELATED TO CAPSAICIN.

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The naturally occurring pungent principles like piperine, capsaicin, fagaramide, spilanthol, pellitorine etc., are found to possess in common the acyl amide -N-CO- linking, the amine being either primary or secondary. It may be purely aliphatic, *viz.*, isobutylamine in fagaramide or fat-aromatic like vanillylamine (in capsaicin) or heterocyclic like piperidine (in piperine). The acid is either aliphatic or fat-aromatic and in all the naturally occurring pungent principles, hitherto investigated, contains at least one ethylenic linkage.

(Piperine)

(Capsaicin)

(Fagaramide)

(Spilanthol)

(Pellitorine, position of double bonds unknown.)

A number of synthetic pungent principles have also been prepared and studied. Thus Scholtz (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1196) has found that the homologues of piperine and further the piperidine of methylene caffeic acid have got the piperine taste.

Nelson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 1115; 1920, 42, 597; Nelson and Dawson, 1923, 45, 2179) after establishing the constitution of capsaicin

prepared and studied the vanillylamides of acetic, propionic, butyric, isobutyric, *n*-hexoic, *n*-heptoic, *n*-octoic, *n*-nonoic, *n*-decoic, crotonic and Δ^9 -undecylenic acids. He found that the pungency as determined by Pearson's method (*Pharm. J.*, 1919, 103, 78) increased until it reached a maximum in *n*-nonovanillylamide and then decreased as the molecular weight increased.

Ott and Zimmerman (*Annalen*, 1921, 425, 314) found that the vanillylamides of unsaturated acids, especially oleovanillylamide, were very pungent while stearovanillylamide was tasteless. So they concluded that the pungency was associated with unsaturation in the acyl group. They also prepared the benzylamide as well as the methoxy- and hydroxybenzylamide of undecylenic acid and found that while the benzylamide and methoxybenzylamide were tasteless, 2-hydroxy- and 4-hydroxybenzylamides were pungent.

Nelson (*loc. cit.*) as well as Lapworth and Royle (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1109) prepared the methyl ether of capsaicin and found that it was much less pungent than capsaicin. Nelson and Dawson (*loc. cit.*) had shown that capsaicin and hydrogenated capsaicin were equally pungent. At least in this case, therefore, unsaturation has no influence on pungency.

Jones and Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2588) using mainly Nelson's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 2121) prepared the vanillylamides of various acids including aliphatic normal and branched chain acids, benzoic acid, saturated ω -phenyl-fatty acids and halogeno-acetic acids. Besides they prepared substituted benzylamides of *n*-nonoic and Δ^9 -undecylenic acids. They observed that while the vanillylamides of saturated phenyl fatty acids were pungent, benzovanillylamide was only faintly so. Cinnamovanillylamide was practically tasteless, while its dihydro derivative was pungent. Some of the aliphatic acid compounds were pungent, while others were practically devoid of pungency. Of the substituted benzylamides of the acids mentioned above, those containing phenolic hydroxyl groups were pungent, while methoxy and methylenedioxy compounds were tasteless.

We have synthesised a number of acylated isobutylamines to see if the pungency depends in any way on the lengths of the carbon chains, on the position of the double bonds, if any, and also on the character of the acids, aliphatic or aromatic or fat-aromatic.

Our conclusions are as follows —

(1) isobutylamides of Δ^3 -heptenoic and Δ^2 -nonenoic acids are equally strongly pungent. *n*-Heptoisobutylamide is next in order of pungency, which therefore decreases to some extent with saturation,

(2) *Benzoisobutylamide* is also very pungent but *anisobutylamide* is practically devoid of pungency.

(3) The *isobutylamide* of n -hexoic, Δ^2 -hexenoic, n -octoic, Δ^2 -octenoic and Δ^3 -decylenic acids are equally pungent but the pungency is of a lower order.

(4) The *isobutylamide* of Δ^8 -undecylenic acid is very feebly pungent hence the pungency decreases when the acyl chain is long and the unsaturated linking remote from the $-N-CO-$ group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

n-Hexoisobutylamide.—Caproic acid (1 mol., 12 g.) and thionyl chloride (8 c.c.) were taken in a flask (250 c.c.) fitted with a condenser, dropping funnel and $CaCl_2$ guard tubes. It was warmed on the water-bath and shaken from time to time until the evolution of gases ceased. The flask was cooled in ice and nearly 100 c.c. of sodium-dried benzene were added. *isoButylamine* (2 mol., 15 g.) was added drop by drop from the tap funnel, the flask being vigorously shaken after each addition. It was allowed to stand overnight and then warmed on the water-bath for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After cooling, water was added and then the flask was warmed on the water-bath for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. Finally the oily layer was extracted with ether and washed successively with water, very dilute hydrochloric acid, water, soda solution and finally again with water. After drying over anhydrous calcium chloride, the ether-benzene mixture was distilled off from a water-bath. The residue was kept in a vacuum desiccator for a day and then distilled at $136^\circ/9$ mm. (Found: N, 8.22. $C_{10}H_{21}ON$ requires N, 8.19 per cent).

Δ^2 -*Hexenoisobutylamide*.—Hexenoic acid was prepared by condensing n -butylaldehyde with malonic acid in presence of piperidine and purified according to the method of Fittig (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2667). The acyl chloride prepared in the usual manner was condensed with *isobutylamine* without a solvent as it was found that when anhydrous ether or benzene was used the yield of the amide was very poor. It boiled at $138^\circ/4$ mm. (Found: N, 8.27. $C_{10}H_{19}ON$ requires N, 8.28 per cent).

n-Heptoisobutylamide.—*n*-Heptoic acid was prepared by oxidising oenanthol according to the method of Grimshaw and Schorlemmer (*Annalen*, 1873, 170, 141). The chloride of the acid was condensed with *isobutylamine* in presence of dry benzene. It boils at $130^\circ/7$ mm. (Found: N, 7.93. $C_{11}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 7.57 per cent).

Δ^2 -*Heptenoisobutylamide*.—Oenanthylic acid was converted into α -bromo-*oenanthylic ester* according to the method of Rupe, Ronus and Lotz (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 4268). The bromo-ester was converted into Δ^2 -heptenoic ester

by the method of Crossly and LeSueur (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 78, 166). The latter gave on hydrolysis heptenoic acid, b.p. 129-132°/20 mm. The amide was prepared in the usual manner, b.p. 140°/4mm. (Found: N, 7.49. $C_{11}H_{21}ON$ requires N, 7.65 per cent).

n-Octoisobutylamide.—The chloride of caprylic acid was condensed with isobutylamine in the usual manner, b.p. 155°/8mm. (Found: N, 7.32. $C_{12}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 7.03 per cent).

Δ^2 -Octenoisobutylamide.—Caprylic acid was converted into α -bromocaprylic ester according to the method of Auwers and Bernhardt (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 2223) and the bromo-ester converted into Δ^2 -octenoic acid according to Crossley and LeSueur (*loc. cit.*). The ester gave on hydrolysis Δ^2 -octenoic acid, which was condensed with isobutylamine in the usual manner, b.p. 150°/4 mm. (Found: N, 7.22. $C_{12}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 7.11 per cent).

Δ^2 -Nonenoisobutylamide.— Δ^2 -Nonenoic acid was prepared according to the method of Harding and Weizmann (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 301) and purified by the hypiodous acid method (Bougault, *Compt. rend.*, 1904, 139, 864). The amide prepared in the usual manner boils at 170°/7 mm. (Found: N, 6.90. $C_{13}H_{25}ON$ requires N, 6.63 per cent).

Δ^3 -Decylenoisobutylamide.—Distillation of *n*-hexylparaconic acid, prepared according to the method of Fittig (*Annalen*, 1885, 227, 90) yielded Δ^3 -decylenic acid, the chloride of which was condensed with isobutylamine, b.p. 155°/4 mm. (Found: N, 6.06. $C_{14}H_{27}ON$ requires N, 6.22 per cent).

Δ^w -Undecylenoisobutylamide.— Δ^w -Undecylenic acid was prepared from castor oil according to the method of Jones and Pyman (*loc. cit.*). Δ^w -Undecylenoisobutylamide boils at 175°/5mm. (Found: N, 5.89. $C_{15}H_{29}ON$ requires N, 5.86 per cent).

Benzoyl, anisoyl and cinnamoyl chlorides were condensed with isobutylamine in the usual manner. *Benzoisobutylamide*, melts at 55° (Found: N, 8.13. $C_{11}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 7.91 per cent). *Anisobutylamide* melts at 105-106° (Found: N, 6.93. $C_{12}H_{27}O_2N$ requires N, 6.76 per cent). *Cinnamobutylamide* melts at 114° (Found: N, 6.98. $C_{13}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 6.90 per cent).

The pungency was determined by Pearson's method (*loc. cit.*) in each case. Alcoholic solutions (1%) of the compounds were prepared. From each solution, a known volume was pipetted out and diluted with an equal volume of alcohol. A few drops were placed on the tongue and the result noted. The dilution was continued until a few drops when put on the tongue did not produce any perceptible effect.